

Dermatosurgical Rounds: Modified Rhomboid Flap for Reconstruction of a Skin Defect Following BCC Excision in the Nasal Area

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Abstract

The reconstructive ladder remains a foundational concept in dermatosurgery and reconstructive field, guiding clinicians toward the simplest effective technique for addressing a certain defect. However, in the context of modern innovations and increasingly personalized surgical planning, individualized modifications to established techniques may offer the most appropriate approach for each patient.

We present a case of a patient with small-to-medium primary defect following excision of a skin cancer involving two nasal subunits - the dorsum nasi and right lateral sidewall. Based on the reconstructive ladder and the characteristics of the defect, a local transposition flap (rhomboid flap) was selected. During the intervention, a modification of the classical flap design was performed. At the one-month postoperative evaluation, the patient exhibited preserved nasal function and contour, along with an excellent cosmetic outcome.

Introduction

The term “from the reconstructive ladder to the reconstructive elevator” has long been used in reconstructive surgery to illustrate the transition from a stepwise, conservative approach to a more individualized-focused strategy [1,2]. The traditional reconstructive ladder - traceable to ancient Egyptian medical texts - emphasizes progressing from the simplest effective technique to more complex procedures, taking into account personal factors, risk, anatomical considerations, and procedural complexity [3].

Although primary closure or skin grafting represents the lower steps of this ladder, these methods do not always ensure optimal functional or cosmetic outcomes [3]. They may carry significant risks, including wound

dehiscence, distortion of critical anatomical structures, graft failure, and suboptimal aesthetic results [3].

When defects are unsuitable for primary closure, the next appropriate step within the ladder-based framework is reconstruction with a local flap [4].

A rhomboid flap, first described by Alexander Limber in 1928, is a versatile and reliable transposition flap widely used for small-to-medium sized cutaneous defects across various anatomical regions [5]. Its classic design consists of a rhomboid with two 120° angles and two 60° angles [6]. The flap, composed of skin and subcutaneous tissue, is transposed around a pivot point into the adjacent defect and its viability depends on the dermal-subdermal plexus and blood supply [5,6].

We present a case of a patient with clinically suspected basal cell carcinoma involving two nasal subunits - the

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dorsum nasi and right lateral sidewall. Surgical excision was recommended. Based on the resulting primary defect and following the principles of the reconstructive ladder, a local transposition flap (a rhomboid flap) was selected as the reconstructive method. During the intervention, a modification was made to the classical design of the flap. One-month postoperatively, the patient demonstrated excellent functional preservation of nasal anatomy and an excellent cosmetic outcome. This report will review the existing literature on the versatility and reliability of the rhomboid flap in nasal reconstruction.

Case report

A 68-year-old male presented to the dermatology department with a primary complaint of a tumorous lesion on the nose, present for approximately 1-2 years. The lesion had previously been treated with liquid nitrogen - without clinical improvement. The patient reported no significant past medical history, and routine laboratory investigations were within the normal range.

Dermatological examination revealed a tumor-like lesion with intermittent bleeding and subsequent crust formation, exhibiting irregular borders and located between the dorsum nasi and the right lateral sidewall (Figure 1). The formation was clinically suspected for basal cell carcinoma. Enlarged lymph nodes were not palpable.

Figure 1: Preoperative View

Tumor-like lesion with intermittent bleeding and subsequent crust formation, exhibiting irregular borders and located between the dorsum nasi and the right lateral sidewall. Immediately after a one-day dressing with povidone iodine - the crust had fallen.

Under local anesthesia with 2% lidocaine diluted with two drops of adrenaline, the lesion was excised, resulting in an irregular circular primary defect. Given the anatomical region - consisting of two nasal subunits (the dorsum nasi and the right lateral sidewall) - and the close proximity of the dorsal nasal artery, external nasal artery, angular vessels, the size of the defect, and regional tension lines (vertical on the mid-dorsum, oblique on the lateral sidewalls, and horizontal at the nasal root), a local transposition flap was selected. A modified rhomboid flap was designed to optimize tissue preservation; therefore, the primary defect was not further reshaped into a perfect rhomboid (Figure 2). The existing defect had a sufficiently rhomboid configuration (ABCD) to allow proper flap transposition.

Figure 2: Intraoperative View

Designing the rhomboid flap (ABCDEF) with the subsequent modification (BG).

Considering the skin laxity in the superior dorsum and nasal root, this area was selected as the donor site because it allowed tension-free closure and ensured that the resultant scar would lie parallel to the horizontal relaxed skin tension lines of the nasal root.

The first incision was planned from point B and extended superiorly toward the nasal root, terminating at point E (with AB equal to BE). A second line, starting from point E and parallel to the defect, was drawn to match the length of the opposite defect side (EF). After careful undermining, the flap was elevated and transposed into the primary defect. Mild tension was noted at point B, necessitating the excision of an additional small triangular segment (in the BG region) to facilitate proper adaptation.

The final defect was closed using single interrupted polypropylene sutures. Histopathological evaluation

confirmed basal cell carcinoma, staged as pT1NxMx with clear surgical margins. Postoperatively, the patient developed edema (Figure 3a) for which cold compresses were given. Additional therapy included metamizole sodium and/or tramadol hydrochloride (1 ampoule as needed), methylprednisolone 32 mg i.v. once daily according to a tapering regimen (32 mg once daily for two days, followed by 20 mg once daily for three days), famotidine 40 mg twice daily, and levocetirizine dihydrochloride 5 mg once daily. The edema was managed at postoperative day 7 (Figure 3b).

Figure 3: Postoperative View: 1-Day Postoperative with Mild Edema (a) and 7-Days Postoperative Follow Up (b)

Figure 4: Postoperative View: 1-Month Postoperative Follow Up

Upon discharge, outpatient management included daily dressings with povidone iodine, ciprofloxacin 500 mg twice daily for 7 days per os, methylprednisolone 4 mg according to a 12-day tapering schedule per os, and esomeprazole 20 mg twice daily for 12 days. At the 1-month postoperative follow up, the nasal contour had begun to harmonize gradually with the surrounding facial structures, resulting in preserved function and an aesthetically pleasing outcome without any signs of facial distortion (Figure 4).

Discussion

The rhomboid flap, characterized by its quadrilateral configuration with four equal-length sides and opposing equal acute and obtuse angles resembling a rhombus, is a versatile local transposition flap commonly used for small-to-medium-sized cutaneous defects, particularly in head and neck reconstruction following surgical excision [7].

“Rhombic” flaps differ in terminology: a rhombic flap refers to a defect designed as a perfect rhombus, whereas rhomboid is often used more broadly for parallelogram-like variations [7]. Several modifications of the classic rhombic design have been described, including the Limberg, Dufourmental, Webster, Quaba-Sommerlad, and note flaps, each offering tailored solutions based on defect geometry, surrounding tissue laxity, and patient-specific anatomical considerations [7].

Alexander Limberg first introduced the rhomboid flap in 1945 but published his results in 1966 (8). His original design employed a rhombus-shaped defect that allows predictable and efficient transposition of the flap into the recipient site [8]. Over time, different variations have emerged, underscoring the flap’s adaptability and its applicability across many anatomical regions with only minor modifications [7].

Modifications of the classic rhombic design have been described [7], although much of the published literature emphasizes mathematical principles rather than clinical application [9]. A clinically focused approach is presented by Quaba et al [9], who reported successful use of modified techniques in 175 reconstructions, including cases in which the defect was not rhomboid-shaped (rather than a circle) and the flap was intentionally designed smaller than the defect. These adaptations offer notable advantages: unnecessary tissue does not need to be sacrificed to create a perfect rhomboid defect, and designing a flap smaller than the defect allows adjacent tissue to contribute to closure, facilitating easier donor-site management. In our case, the primary defect had a slight rhomboid configuration but was not further reshaped, and the flap was designed smaller than the defect. Additionally, a small triangular was excised. These intraoperative modifications enabled preservation of nasal function and contour, avoidance

of structural distortion, and an aesthetically pleasing postoperative outcome.

Although some defects can be managed with primary closure or skin grafting, a well-planned rhomboid flap - with the final scar aligned parallel to relaxed skin tension lines - often provides superior functional and cosmetic results by preserving adjacent skin texture and color [6].

While skin grafts may appear to offer a simpler reconstructive option, they require strict postoperative immobilization, delay functional recovery, require hygiene restrictions, and may yield suboptimal aesthetic outcomes [6].

In contrast, the rhomboid flap remains a safe and efficient technique, offering time-efficiency, preservation of local anatomy and excellent cosmetic integration [6]. Its versatility is well documented across a range of reconstructive scenarios, including breast reconstruction [10] and defect reconstruction after antecubital contractures [11].

Conclusion

Our result aligns with the international findings supporting the effectiveness of rhomboid flaps across numerous anatomical regions. When combined with intraoperative modifications, this technique allows the surgeon to reconstruct defects safely while maintaining the integrity, color, and texture of surrounding tissues. In our case, the applied modifications preserved nasal function and contour, prevented structural distortion, and resulted in an aesthetically favorable postoperative outcome.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethical Approval

Ethics approval statement is not required.

Informed Consent

Written informed consent for publication of their details was obtained from the patient.

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